

A Study of Prevalence of Computer Vision Syndrome in MBBS Students at a Medical College**B Jyothi¹, Valluru Pragna²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar, Telangana²Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar, Telangana

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Abstract

Background: Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS), or digital eye strain, is a group of eye and vision-related problems resulting from prolonged use of digital screens such as computers, smartphones, and tablets. Symptoms include eye strain, dryness, headaches, blurred vision, and neck pain. The condition is increasingly prevalent with rising screen time, highlighting the need for awareness and preventive measures. This study was done to determine the prevalence of CVS in medical students of this institute.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study conducted after obtaining written consent from medical students, of a medical college and hospital. Data collected included demographic profiles, patterns of computer/mobile and visual display terminal usage, symptoms of computer vision syndrome (CVS), and precautions taken to mitigate its effects. Analysis was performed using SPSS version 22 in Windows format.

Results: The prevalence of CVS in our study was approximately 71.5% of the study participants exhibited symptoms of CVS, indicating a high prevalence. Prolonged Screen Time: A strong association between increased screen usage and the development of CVS symptoms was observed. Over 64% of participants spent more than 3 hours daily on digital screens. While refractive surgery can be a factor, other factors like prolonged screen time and environmental conditions seem to play a more significant role in the development of dry eye. Approximately 10.8% of participants had undergone refractive surgery.

Conclusion: From the data arising out of the present study it can be safely concluded that well over three-fourths of the medical students and faculty had developed at least one or other form of CVS. Headache was the most common complaint reported (24%) followed by eye strain (11%). These other common symptoms included dry eye, eye strain, and blurred vision. Likewise, the Students who used mobiles or laptops for more than 2 hours a day as compared to those with less than 2 hours of usage had increased chances of developing CVS symptoms if protective measures such as display filters were not used.

Keywords: Computer Vision Syndrome, Digital Screen Time, Refractive Errors, Dry Eye.

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Introduction

There is no doubt that technological development over the last two decades especially the shift from computers to laptops and now smartphones has greatly transformed our lives. Initially, it was expected that such devices would be an extravagance, however, they are currently practically indispensable throughout work, education, and leisure. According to the statistics, by 2020 about 90% of new vacancies indicated obligatory computer literacy [1, 2]. But there are negative consequences in this case too: even spending two hours a day with screens has consequences on the systemic, ocular, and psychosomatic levels. According to the American Optometric Association Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) is a group of integrated systemic

and ocular disorders resulting from extended near work from computing devices, energy-saving displays, cell phones, tablet standards, and e-book readers [3]. Some of the symptoms include headaches, strained eyes, seeing the object as two, redness and sensations of burning, and blurred vision. These problems tend to be worse in low light, air-conditioned environments, especially if they spend a lot of time on screens [4].

Systemic complaints such as neck, back, wrist, and joint pain are also linked to extended hours of computer use, further contributing to stress and discomfort. Studies indicate that excessive screen time—over 30 hours per week or sustained usage for more than a decade—can increase the risk of psychosomatic disorders and depression [5, 6].

Among the various symptoms, ocular issues are most prevalent, making CVS a widespread epidemic, with prevalence rates ranging from 64% to 90% among computer users in urban areas. The rise of smartphones has significantly contributed to the increasing prevalence of CVS [7]. Affordable internet data plans, widespread availability of smartphones, and their early adoption, especially in countries like India—the second-largest smartphone market globally—have amplified this issue. India has around 800 million registered mobile users, with 60% using smartphones. Prolonged smartphone use, particularly in dim lighting conditions such as at night, leads to eye strain, irritation, redness, and blurred vision, all symptoms of CVS. Overuse of smartphones, often reaching levels of addiction, has been classified as a behavioural problem under the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) [8]. Studies report that 39–44% of young individuals in India and over 30% of participants in South Korea show a risk of smartphone addiction [8, 9]. Behavioural studies in Malaysia reveal that more than 65% of participants experience some degree of dependency [10]. Continuous smartphone use reduces blinking rates and strains facial, neck, and shoulder muscles, leading to fatigue and blurred vision. Reading on small screens, especially in bed, disrupts sleep cycles by reducing melatonin levels due to blue light emissions from digital screens. This interference with non-REM sleep can result in chronic fatigue and other sleep-related issues. Despite the growing prevalence of CVS and related health concerns, there is a notable lack of survey-based studies on young adults in India, particularly among medical students. This highlights the need for targeted research to understand the scale of CVS in this demographic and develop effective strategies for prevention and management. As technology continues to advance and integrate into daily life, awareness of its potential health effects is essential. By fostering better habits, improving screen ergonomics, and encouraging breaks during prolonged use, individuals can mitigate the impact of screen overuse on their overall well-being. This study was carried out at our institution to find the prevalence of computer vision syndrome in the medical students of our college.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional survey was carried out by the Department of Ophthalmology, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Naganoor, Karimnagar, Telangana. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study. Participants completed a pre-tested, pre-structured questionnaire that captured their demographic information, daily usage patterns and preferences, hours spent on Video Display Terminals (VDTs, referring to computer/mobile screens using LCD or LED technology), common complaints related to device use, and their knowledge and attitudes about Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS). The questionnaire also included queries about sleep disturbances, willingness to address CVS, and precautions taken to prevent its progression.

Inclusion Criteria: The study included MBBS students, from our medical college/hospital who had been using mobile phones and computers for at least one month before the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Participants with a history of chronic systemic illness, those on medication for current medical conditions, and those who did not provide consent were excluded.

Statistical Analysis: All the data was gathered refined and uploaded to MS Excel spreadsheet. The data was analyzed by SPSS version 21 in Windows format. The continuous variables were represented as mean, standard deviation, and percentages. The categorical variables were calculated by chi-square test and the values of p (<0.05) were considered as significant.

Results

A total of 200 questionnaire forms were distributed across the study participants based on the inclusion criteria. 158 participants returned the forms filled and signed successfully. The response rate was 69%. Total number of male participants was 85 (53.7%) while the female participants were 73 (46.2%). The male-to-female ratio was 1:0.8. The youngest participant was 19 years of age, and the oldest participant was 26 years of age. The mean age of the participants was 20.5 ± 5.5 years. The detailed distribution of students across the years is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of students included in the study

Student	Male (%)	Female (%)	Percentage
First-year	16 (18.8%)	15 (17.6%)	31 (19.6%)
Second Year	22 (25.9%)	18 (21.2%)	40 (25.3%)
Third year	19 (22.3%)	21 (24.7%)	40 (25.3%)
Fourth year	28 (32.9%)	19 (22.3%)	47 (29.7%)
Total	85 (100.0%)	73 (100.0%)	158 (100.0%)

The participants were asked to determine the digital screen usage time in hours based on the digital well-being statistics from the electronic devices. Table 2 depicts the results of digital screen time it shows that a significant portion of participants

(64.1%) spend between 1 to 3 hours per day on digital screens. A considerable number of individuals (45.9%) engage in screen activities for more than 3 hours daily. A relatively small group (44.3%) uses digital screens for less than an hour per day.

Table 2: Showing the digital screen usage time in hours in the participants of the study

Amount of digital screen time in hours per day	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1 hour	7	44.3
1 – 2 hours	44	27.8
2 – 3 hours	36	22.8
3 – 5 hours	38	24.0
5 – 6 hours	21	13.3
> 6 hours	12	7.6
Total	158	100

The distribution of symptoms reported by the subjects included in the study is depicted in Table 3 some of the responses overlap. Headache, eye strain, difficulty focusing, and neck pain were the most frequently reported symptoms, indicating their significant prevalence among study participants. Eye-related symptoms like dry eyes, redness,

blurred vision, and double vision were also commonly reported, highlighting the impact of excessive screen time on visual health. Symptoms like fatigue, disturbed sleep, and pain in fingers suggest that the effects of computer vision syndrome can extend beyond ocular discomfort.

Table 3: Distribution of symptoms reported in the responses of the study (multiple responses)

Symptoms	Frequency	Percentage
Headache	37	23.4
Fatigue	11	6.9
Dry eye	10	6.3
Redness in the eye	11	6.9
Blurred vision	18	11.4
Double vision	12	7.6
Eye strain	16	10.1
Difficulty in focussing	17	10.7
Neck pain	20	12.6
Disturbed sleep	18	11.4
Pain in fingers	14	8.8
Headache in morning	19	12.0

The Prevalence of CVS was calculated using: (Number of participants with CVS / Total participants) * 100% = (113 / 158) * 100% ≈ 72%. Approximately 72% of the study participants exhibited

symptoms of Computer Vision Syndrome. This suggests a high prevalence of CVS among the population studied (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Showing the prevalence of computer vision syndrome in the cohort

The Prevalence of Dry Eye: 22 out of 158 participants (approximately 14%) reported experiencing dry eye symptoms. Refractive Surgery: A relatively

small number of participants (17 out of 158, or approximately 10.8%) had undergone refractive surgery.

Figure 2: Analyzing Dry Eye and Refractive Surgery in the Cohort

Figure 3 analyzing digital screen usage years shows that a significant proportion of participants (85%) have been using digital screens for more than a

year. A substantial number (46%) have been using screens for 3-5 years. A smaller group (25%) have been using screens for less than a year.

Figure 3: Digital screen usage in years in the cohort

Discussion

In recent times, the advent of mobile and computer-based technology has raised the age of being 'always on'. Smartphones along with computers have become major interfaces through which internet connection and a constantly progressive outside environment can be accessed and manipulated by using small screens. Of the electronic devices, smartphones, in particular, are now owned by virtually every teenager, and most adults. Also, people's leisure activity has changed with the availability of social networks Facebook, Twitter, YouTube; mobile games; game consoles PlayStation. However, this screen time interferes with personal, social, and family relations and can produce long-term effects [11].

To achieve this goal in the current study, the authors sought to estimate the level of CVS

symptoms among the MBBS students of a medical col-

lege in Telangana. As expected, more than 90% of the students mentioned using smartphones for more than 2 hours daily, mainly touchscreen exposing them to CVS. About 65% of students often use their smartphones to watch multimedia products, including movies or television series. CVS was present in 22 of the participants, giving a prevalence of 72%; while 2 participants reported eye strain, 6 participants complained of headaches. This suggests that there are higher CVS prevalence rates in developed countries. Witness that the CVS prevalence was observed to be at 75% in Mutti et al. [12] in the USA and similar to other findings in Europe. In their cross-sectional studies, Mocci et al. [13] in Italy noted a 31.9% asthenopia prevalence as did Sanchez et al. [14] in the Spanish population

with a prevalence rate of 68.5%. Bhandari et al. [15] completed a study in India in which they revealed that 46.3 % of the population complained of asthenopia with symptoms such as asthenopia, eye heaviness, and watering being highlighted as worsening with Prolonged VDT use.

The operational definition of CVS recognizes that gender plays an important part in CVS. For example, males reported more redness, blurring of vision, and dryness of eyes compared to females agreeing to more occurrences of headaches and excessive eye watering. The current study did not identify any difference in symptoms between males and females. Another Chennai study noting CVS prevalence found that 416 medical and engineering students had a CVS prevalence of 80.3%; engineering students 81.9 % and medical students 78.6% [16]. Medical students experienced headaches in the range of 43% while engineering students experienced headaches in the range of 45%, however, in the current study the prevalence rate of students experiencing headaches was 23.4%. Talwar et al. [17] found 29% of the participants had headaches and several case reports include Sen et al. [18] 61% and Kesavachandran et al. [19] 17%. A cross-sectional study of 795 university students from Malaysia by Reddy et al. [20] revealed that 89.9% of the students had CVS, 18% had headaches and 17% had eye strain. Reddy et al. [20] also said that symptoms begin to emerge when children spend over 3 hours in front of screens. In the same way, a nationwide study conducted in Sri Lanka revealed a CVS prevalence of 67.4 % in the population with the current study showing 72%. This Sri Lankan study also presented headaches (45%), dry eye (31%), and eye pain (28%) as frequent symptoms [21]. In addition, a history of eye-related disease and contact lens use greatly contributed to the results. Mobile/computer usage of more than two hours per day was a significant predictor of CVS symptoms; participants who used screens for less than an hour per day complained significantly less about their vision. According to Shrivastava and Bhoobhate, the complaints based on visual symptoms became more prominent as the screen time was longer, while Rehman and Sanip also found that participants with CVS used VDTs for more than 7 hours per day. According to Mutti et al. [22], symptoms were severe if subjected to VDT for, 8 to 9 hours, a fact supported by another study [23].

Conclusion

From the data arising out of the present study, it can be safely concluded that well over three-fourths of the medical students and faculty had developed at least one or other form of CVS. Headache was the most common complaint reported (24%) followed by eye strain (11%). These other common symptoms included dry eye, eye strain, and blurred

vision. Likewise, the Students who used mobiles or laptops for more than 2 hours a day as compared to those with less than 2 hours of usage had increased chances of developing CVS symptoms if protective measures such as display filters were not used. The visual symptoms of CVS were significantly higher in participants who previously reported dry eye or who had undergone refractive surgery. More follow-up investigations are suggested to reproduce and establish the diagnosis of CVS risk factors.

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